

Semantics for Big Data in Emergency Response

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Motivation

Emergency Management (EM) is the iterative handling of man-made or natural emergency-related activities. Dearth of integrated systems and lack of an exact understanding of the situation based on real time information can obstruct effective response.

Envisioned VISIT Platform

The envisioned platform called **Improving Resilience to Emergency Events (VISIT)** collects heterogeneous data from several resources and semantically integrates them to provide decision support services to the **EM Services**. The overall context for VISIT platform lies in the area of **situational awareness** and **Command and Control**. It has five main responsibilities.

- Aggregate multimodal information
- Semantic integration
- Integrate the new knowledge provided by the crowd
- Present aggregated and structured data
- Support direct interaction between users and information provider

Figure 1: VISIT architecture

Role of Semantics in VISIT

The most promising approach is to structure and enrich information semantically, because it simplifies the way to create situation aware queries. Ultimately, it will obtain actionable insights (value) by enhancing semantic representations to make big emergency data more comprehensive and meaningful.

Figure 2: Semantics in VISIT

VISIT Approach to Big Data 4Vs

Two crucial challenges of extracting value (i.e. 5th V) need to be overcome if VISIT is to succeed.

- Ability to obtain and deploy knowledge from heterogeneous data and integrate it with declarative domain knowledge.
- Ability to learn and deploy domain models from different sensor streams for classification, prediction, decision making and even penalisation.

Big Data characteristic	Challenge	VISIT approach
Volume	Ability to abstract the heterogeneous multimodal data, that is to change the level of abstraction for data processing to gain insights for decision making.	Integrates logical reasoning into an integrated semantic context that helps merging and conceptualising multimodal data and search for pertinent information to diminish ambiguity and incompleteness.
Velocity	Ability to process data quickly and to refine relevant historical knowledge.	Ontologies support in formal conceptual modelling of evolving, dynamic events and social knowledge supported semantic models help in making real-time (social and sensor) data understandable.
Variety	Continuous monitoring during emergency is ensuing in smooth multimodal data streams, so the appropriate situational knowledge to analyse data has to be developed.	domain models are important for prediction and decision making in real-time from the sensed data.
Veracity	As the availability of multimodal (including social media) data increases, the task of identifying high-quality content based on user contributions becomes increasingly important.	The assessment of the quality of the content in social media adds a significant layer of complexity over traditional data quality assessment frameworks. A semantically enabled integration of physical and sensor data can improve assessing data trustworthiness in VISIT.